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FOREGROUND OBJECT DETECTION AND REALISM ASSESSMENT WITH THE BACKGROUND IMAGE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a robust foreground object detection algorithm which can counter the effects of illumination changes and noise , and thus providing an optimal choice for intelligent video surveillance systems using static cameras. An Online Expectation Maximization (E-M) algorithm is used in combination with a spherical K-means clustering method for accurate updation of gaussian mixture models when there are changes due to illuminations. The results of the former step is enhanced by the linear RGB color feature of reflection radiance from object surfaces under different environmental illuminations. A statistical framework is used for the foreground object detection. Noise at this stage is reduced further using a Bayesian iterative decision-making technique. Various comparative experiments show that the proposed algorithm outcompetes several classical methods on several datasets , both in detection performance and in robustness to perturbations from illumination changes.

Keywords: *Bayesian, ExpectationMaximization, Guassian mixture models, reflection radiance, robustness*

I. INTRODUCTION

Video surveillance plays a major role in several applications namely indoor security systems , traffic and transportation, manufacturing safety, and defense technology. Intelligent and autonomous video surveillance systems has been developed as a result of the advancement in the development of computer vision, pattern recognition, and image processing technology. As a first step the system learns the features of input scene to gain knowledge about the unknown object. In various situations, this modeling of the scene is required. It is always a best choice to explain the modeling problem using a mixture of pdfs involving the background part of the scene rather than using a

stochastic process with a pixel presentation of a small portion of the scene over a period of time. After the generation of the model the foreground is extracted from the obtained mixtures using a foreground detection method for performing higher level processing.

1.1 Nature of the problem

In a practical observation, , especially under unstable illumination conditions. Though the camera is static, the scene can be dynamic with full of noise. Global illumination changes are found everywhere in an outdoor surveillance environment, where there are illuminations from sunlight. The fast changes in global illumination deteriorate the object detection results from simple false alarms to breakdown of the whole system. Whenever the direct light from a light source is obstructed by an object only ambient light reaches the shadowed area. This results in the decline of brightness of a local region. A good foreground detection algorithm should adapt to both global and local illumination changes.

1.2 Contribution of the paper

In this paper, we propose an foreground detection algorithm with a realism assessment method that follows it. To enhance the results of foreground object detection , three main contributions are presented. The first contribution is an explicit spectral reflection model analysis of object surfaces in RGB space under changing illumination conditions. The distributions in RGB color space present a linear pattern irrespective of the color changes of the object due to the environment illumination. The second contribution involves the framework of the statistical background modeling process, in which the online expectation-maximization (EM) theory and the spherical K-means clustering algorithm are combined to update a Gaussian mixture model (GMM). The online expectation maximization theory presents a simple and effective update scheme for GMM parameters, and the spherical K-means clustering algorithm takes advantage of the aforementioned RGB color feature to provide accurate scene modeling direction under unstable illumination. The final contribution consists of two steps. The first step is a coarse foreground detection method that finds its basis in the previously established GMM background model. The second step uses an iterative decision-making strategy to improve the binary detection mask obtained in the first step. A Markov random field utilizes the spatial signal and computes the prior probability of the pixel in the form of a Gibbs distribution at every iteration, thus reduces the scattering of false alarms.

1.3 Related Work

There has been much research in the field of scene learning and foreground detection. Kalman filters which can resist sharp illumination changes were used by many researchers to model the background .It has a restricted modeling ability for complex scenes. The Hidden Markov model (HMM) , an effective tool in voice recognition and can also be applied in background modeling . The main disadvantage of HMMs is that eventhough they produce good results in representing dynamic backgrounds, the high computational cost renders them undesirable.The Pfunder surveillance system introduced a single Gaussian distribution to model each pixel .But due to lot of unknown information in the single Gaussian model because of fast processing speed, the system resulted with a bad representation when facing dynamic scenes. The classical background modeling algorithm for surveillance systems proposed by Stauffer and Grimson set up a GMM to explain all the possibilities of ground truth per pixel. This mixture updates all the parameters in an exponential decay manner with the latest input. Foreground is then easily extracted by matching the mixture with the input.

Figueiredo and Jain employed a component-wise batch EM algorithm for the learning of finite mixtures and their data clustering method gave a fresh perspective to scene modeling. Zivkovic and Heijden developed an online maximum *a posteriori* (MAP) EM algorithm to realize the unsupervised learning of mixtures. They applied the method to background learning for the background subtraction. Kim *et al.* built a codebook model for background and developed a fast foreground extraction method based on RGB color space.Gao *et al.* extended the method, and used a hierarchical scheme with block-based and pixel-based codebooks for foreground detection . Liu *et al.* followed the

HSV model to detect foreground and remove cast shadows and used Markov random field (MRF) to suppress cast shadow and false detections.

Few other researchers used a kernel density estimation (KDE) in the srgb color space to detection of foreground and also for the elimination of shadows. B.lei and L.Xu formulated a Three brightness metrics based on the conversion equation of RGB to YUV color space for the extraction of shadow pixels and highlighted (brightened) regions from the foreground mask. Local texture information is discovered to be robust against illumination variations to some extent. Y.Tian ,M.lu ,and A.Hampapur compared the gradient information of a neighborhood centered at a foreground position in both the background image and the latest frame for the removal of spurious foreground pixels. In the physical world, color can be decomposed into a spectrum that covers a range of wavelengths. The color appearance of an object is influenced by the spectral power distribution of the incident light and the surface properties. The dichromatic reflection model was used to recover the total surface-spectral reflectance of objects in a scene by eliminating the influence of illumination from the measured color signals. The unique body reflectances of objects were then classified into different groups to realize object recognition.

Salvador *et al.* proposed a cast shadow segmentation algorithm for both still and moving images, in which the c1c2c3-invariant color feature was derived from the dichromatic reflection model. J.M.Choi , Y.J.Yoo,and J.Y.Choi used a Lambertian reflection model to detection and elimination of the shadow of a moving object through three cascaded estimators. R.Lenz used Lie theory and a reflection model for the estimation of the dynamic properties of changing illumination. Geusebroek *et al.* studied on various geometrical color-invariant expressions, describing material properties in RGB images from the reflection theory of Kubelka-Munk.Gevers and Smeulders derived a series of color invariants in an RGB color space by reflection model analysis in a photometric color-invariant image retrieval system. Some researchers focuses on detection and removal of shadows in realtime image analysis to obtain accurate foregrounds of moving objects.

Prati *et al.* discussed on shadow detection of moving objects and evaluated their detection performance by comparing consecutive experiments. Zhang *et al.* utilized the illumination invariant ratio edge to classify each moving pixel into foreground object or moving shadow.T.Gevers and A.Smeulders presented a very fast background subtraction and shadow detection method for monochromatic video sequences .They used the local statistical information and also conducted tests to remove cast shadows on the detection mask. The majority of work on eliminating spurious foreground (i.e., shadows or highlights) first needs to detect a contaminated foreground mask and then uses different cues to discriminate shadowed area from foreground. Moreover, few works handle global illumination changes in practical environments. Horprasert *et al.* proposed a background subtraction method for foreground object detection. However, their background model, constructed in a batch manner using a series of past images, is simple and unimodal.

Foreground detection is one of the branches of the change detection application. The significant use of the change detection algorithm is that , it tries to separate the changes caused by foreground movements from the changes that are due to noise and the effects of scene illumination. An intelligent scene monitoring system can be greatly affected by illumination by changing the color appearance of the scene. To counter these illumination changes researchers have turned to different color spaces thar remains invariant to illumination changes.

II.FOREGROUND OBJECT DETECTION

Foreground detection has been used extensively in many applications such as people counting, traffic monitoring and face recognition. However, most of the existing detectors can only work under limited conditions. This happens because of the inability of the detector to distinguish foreground and background pixels, especially in complex situations. Our aim is to improve the robustness of foreground detection under sudden and gradual illumination change, colour similarity issue, moving background and shadow noise. Since it is hard to achieve robustness using a single model, we have combined several methods into an integrated system. The masked grey world algorithm is introduced to handle sudden illumination change. Colour co-occurrence modeling is then fused with the probabilistic edge-based background modeling. Colour co-occurrence modeling is good in filtering

moving background and robust to gradual illumination change, while an edge-based modelling is used for solving a colour similarity problem. Finally, an extended conditional random field approach is used to filter out shadow and afterimage noise. Simulation results show that our algorithm performs better compared to the existing methods, which makes it suitable for higher-level applications.

2.1 Video Surveillance System

Fig 1.1 Video Surveillance system architecture diagram

The current image is given as input where the image is background estimated and the object is extracted. This consists of detection phase and the object is tracked and the decision is made by the event recognition.

2.2 Stages of detection

The stages of detection of foreground object is

- Preprocessing
- Modeling and Coarse Foreground Detection
- Tuning
- Realism Assessment
- Re coloring Methods
- Unrealistic Comparisons

2.2.1 Preprocessing

Input video is processed and frames extraction will be taken in this module. Input image rgb is converted as grayscale image in the binary coding process.

Fig 1.2 Demo screen shot

Fig 1.3 Frames in windows

Fig 1.4 Input video sequence image captured by the sensor

2.2.2 Modeling and Coarse Foreground Detection

Fast illumination changes are encountered, but the video is recorded from a shaking camera under a wind load. We sampled 282 consecutive frames at a resolution of 720×576 from the original video clip to model the background. The proposed foreground detection algorithm is then evaluated on the *Time of Day (ToD)* sequence in the Wallflower dataset. The lights in this sequence are brightened gradually too.

Fig 1.5 Data set of image samples

Fig 1.6 consecutive frames at a resolution of 720×576 from the original video clip

2.2.3 Tuning

In a real outdoor environment, the situation is more complicated because we may encounter different weather conditions. The optimal parameter configurations for rainy days and clear days should not be the same—the values of parameters for clear days are larger. By employing this empirical knowledge, a self-adaptive scheme can be devised to decide what values we should choose for parameters under different weather conditions.

Fig 1.7 Tuning optimal parameter configurations

2.2.4. Realism Assessment : Color similarity and tendency measurements will be calculated.

- Color Similarity Measure
- Color Tendency Measures

2.2.5 Re coloring Methods

This method can inconspicuously merge the foreground of an image into the background. On the other hand, the re coloring by consistence of color tendency method is especially useful for color adjustment of uniform regions such as sky or water surface. The improvement algorithms and schemes will be applied in the previous stage image.

2.2.6 Unrealistic Comparisons

The inserted object is verified with the merged object then the realism will be analyzed to show the proposed scheme is the best when compared the existing schemes. The realism can be compared by viewing the image as well as with the processed values and ratios.

Fig 1.8 Realism Assessment Comparisons

2.3 Choice of the Model Parameters

The segmentation algorithms described herein depend on a set of parameters, which are mainly the thresholds and the learning rate α . In this scenario, we must figure out which are the best values for the most significant parameters for each algorithm. This was done using ROC curves which display the performance of each algorithm as a function of the parameters. The Receiver Operation Characteristic (ROC) have been extensively used in communications. In this case we have kept the learning rate α constant and varied the thresholds in the attempt to obtain the best threshold value T. We repeated this procedure for several values of α . This requires a considerable number of tests, but in this way it is possible to achieve a proper configuration for the algorithm parameters. Once the parameters are set, we use these values in a different sequence. To ROC curves describe the evolution of the false alarms (FA) and detection failures (DF) as T varies. An ideal curve would be close to the origin, and the area under the curve would be close to zero. To obtain these two values, we compute these measures (for each value of T) by applying the region matching trough the sequence. The final values are computed as the mean values of FA and DF. There is a large number of false alarms in the training sequence due to the presence of a static object (car) which suddenly starts to move. The background image should be modified when the car starts to move. However, the image analysis algorithms are not able to cope with this situation since they only consider slow adaptations of the background. A ghost region is therefore detected in the place where the car was (a false alarm). we use a small α parameter.

Sequence	FP	FN	P	S	F-Score
Waving Trees	2.7	1.5	4.14	98.47	96.26
Walk3	0.1	15.8	82.6	84.18	83.38
LeftBag PickedUp	0.1	44.2	79.1	56.73	66.07
Camouflage	15.3	5.36	88.3	94.64	91.37

Fig 1.9 Result of our method on four sequences

III .CONCLUSION

Thus an effective foreground object detection algorithm was built , which is robust against illumination changes and perturbations for real time video surveillance systems. Different types of illumination changes were overcome using statistical foreground detection algorithm and spherical k-means method. The former was useful in diminishing the effect of illumination changes on the training models whereas the later was able to counteract the effect of sudden illumination fluctuations. The above combination of algorithms was large enough to diminish the effect of shadows during the detection of foreground mask. The Bayesian iterative decision making at each and every pixel in the frame helped largely in the noise reduction process. This foreground detection system can be improved for the medical anomaly detection system. There are so many analyzing and detecting tools in the medical field that tools are working in the principal of anomaly object detection in the normal system. So this object detection can be improved for the medical applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.-F. Lalonde, D. Hoeim, A. A. Efros, C. Rother, J. W. , and A. Criminisi, "Photo clip art," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. , 1–10, Aug. 2007, Article 3.
- [2] J. Jia, J. Sun, C.-K. Tang, and H.-Y. Shum, "Drag-and-drop pasting," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 631–637, Jul. 2006.
- [3] E. Reinhard, M. Adhikhmin, B. Gooch, and P. Shirley, "Color transfer between images," *IEEE Comput. Graph. Appl.*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 34–41, Sep./Oct. 2001.
- [4] P. Pérez, M. Gangnet, and A. Blake, "Poisson image editing," *ACM Trans. Graph.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 313–318, Jul. 2003.
- [5] J.-F. Lalonde and A. A. Efros, "Using color compatibility for assessing image realism," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Computer Vision*, Brazil, 2007, pp. 14–21.
- [6] I. Omer and M. Werman, "Color-lines: Image specific color representation," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Washington, DC, 2004, vol. II, pp. 946–953.
- [7] F. Cutzu, R. Hammoud, and A. Leykin, "Estimating the photorealism of images: Distinguishing paintings from photographs," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Madison, WI, 2003, vol. II, pp. 305–312.
- [8] A. P. Bradley, "The use of the area under the ROC curve in the evaluation of machine learning algorithms," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 1145–1159, 1997.
- [9] C.-C. Chang and C.-J. Lin, LIB SVM: A Library for Support Vector Machines, 2001. [Online]. Available: <http://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/ libsvm>.
- [10] E. Reinhard, A. O. Akyuz, M. Colbert, C. E. Hughes, and M. O'Conner, "Real-time color blending of rendered and captured video," presented at the Interservice/Industry Training, Simulation, and Education Conf., 2004, paper 1502, pp. 1–9.